

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Prediction of di-nucleotide-specific DNA-binding sites in proteins using neural networks

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

Quantitative data will be generated from PDB crystal structures of Protein-DNA complexes (input data) and Neural Network models trained on the input data. Raw data will be saved as .csv and text files. Analysed data will be presented in the form of graphs and images. We expect a data volume of around 1 terabyte to be generated during the analysis.

II. Standards and metadata

We will comply with the DOME-ML and Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) community-wide guidelines, recommendations and checklists for machine learning models.

- **Comprehensive documentation will be provided about:** model's requirements, design, usage, and output formats.
- **Version control:** will be implemented for models model's training data, architecture, hyperparameters, and performance.
- **Analysis pipelines:** will be made available on GitHub with README files.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Existing 3D crystal structures of PDNA complexes from the PDB will be the main source of input data for our analysis.

IV. Secondary use

Data and ML models will be immediately available for secondary reuse by researchers after the publication.

V. Methods for data sharing

After publication, all input datasets will be made publicly available on OpenML. Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace). The models will be assigned a unique and persistent identifier and linked to the model's metadata.

VI. Proprietary data

We do not envisage any restrictions or delays in making the data available. No restrictions will be placed on the data.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be made publicly available immediately after the publication.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

All input data downloaded from the PDB will be in the .pdb format, which is essentially a text format. Raw data will be saved as .csv and text files. Analysed data will be presented in the form of graphs and images. For the analysis and data preparation, Jupyter notebooks in combination with R programming will be used. For Neural Network training and prediction, we intend to use the SNNS software. SNNS models are saved in plain text format, e.g. Neural network architecture and weights file will be saved as “network_name.net”.